

P28 Attribution

Purpose

This version of the HDR UK Attribution Policy applies to outputs generated from HDR UK programmes launched after 31 March 2023 (i.e. HDR UK's second five years).

For outputs generated from HDR UK programmes launched prior to 31 March 2023 (i.e. HDR UK's first five years), please see [Version 1 of the HDR UK Attribution Policy \(June 2019\)](#).

This policy sets out who is required to adhere to this policy, which research outputs should be attributed and how. This includes how team science and the use of patient data should be acknowledged. A key intention of this policy is to clarify how HDR UK will keep track of its research outputs across programmes and other initiatives, enabling reporting on achievements across the whole institute.

Responsibility

It is the responsibility of all Staff, Secondees and Community Members¹ to comply with this policy.

Background

This policy goes beyond setting out how to cite the source of funding for published work and extends to algorithms, code, software and methodologies we generate as part of our strategy to develop safe, secure and scalable health data science tools and technologies, that will demonstrate the power of large-scale health data to address major health challenges.

As well as attributing HDR UK in research outputs, the HDR UK community should also recognise the role of patients and public in providing health data. We also expect all members of research teams, to be recognised, actively demonstrating team science.

This policy aligns with HDR UK's core values:

- *Transparency* - we will incentivise the sharing of information, insights and innovations, in a consistent way (as set out in this policy), and clearly attribute them to HDR UK.

¹ Any individuals in receipt of funding from HDR UK or involved in an HDR UK programme or project including Institute Research Organisation Directors, Associate Directors, Researchers, Scientists, Technologists, Trialists, Fellows and Post Doctoral Researchers, PhD and MSc students

Policy owner: Director of Strategy

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Approved by: SLT

- *Optimism* – we are optimistic that the wider benefits of adhering to this policy, as well as the recognition we offer, will be sufficient incentive to do so and therefore embrace team science.
- *Respect* – of all team members by ensuring all contributors are named on publications and their role acknowledged through use of [CASRAI2's Contributor Roles Taxonomy \(CRediT\) system](#), where possible, as well as acknowledging public and patients who provide their data to help advance medical research.
- *Courage* – this policy goes above and beyond typical academic attribution policies which are often limited to publications. HDR UK recognises that algorithms, code, software and methodologies will be key outputs generated by the HDR UK community and should be made available to researchers and other users with as few restrictions as possible.
- *Humility* – by setting out mechanisms to clearly and consistently attribute both the direct outputs of our work, as well as recognise and celebrate, but not overclaim, where our work has catalysed achievements of other individuals and organisations.

This policy complements the 'Good Research Practice Policy' and 'Brand and Style Guide' – this attribution policy says *who* should attribute, as well as *what*, *how* and *why* outputs should be attributed, whereas:

- [P26 Good Research Practice Policy](#) sets open access requirements including *when* and *where* outputs should be made available, i.e. as soon as possible in open access environments (e.g. open access journals).
- The [Brand and Style Guide](#) goes into more detail on the HDR UK brand identity and how it should be applied across communications more generally (e.g. press releases, where to find HDR UK branded presentation templates, etc).

Attributing HDR UK Research Outputs

Defining the HDR UK Community – to Whom this Policy Applies

We are a distributed institute with partnership at our core - it can be challenging to define who the HDR UK Community is, when we are not all 'under one roof'. So for clarity:

If you are in receipt of funds from HDR UK (e.g. salary, research costs), or involved in an HDR UK project (including where salary is an in-kind contribution), then this attribution policy applies to you.

This includes **Institute Members**, including researchers, scientists, technologists, triallists etc working on HDR UK programmes, HDR UK PhD and MSc students etc. Institute Members, in addition to attributing HDR UK in outputs, should list HDR UK as one of the institutions to which you are affiliated – including in publications and email signatures (e.g., 'Member of Health Data Research UK').

² CASRAI = Consortia Advancing Standards in Research Administration Information

This also includes individual and institutional ***Affiliate Members***, for outputs that have resulted from being part of a team that includes HDR UK Institute Members.

More detail can be found at ***Annex 1***.

Each member of the HDR UK community is required to hold an active **ORCID³** account and provide HDR UK with their ORCID number (please email enquiries@hdruk.ac.uk).

Which Outputs Should be Attributed and How?

Core to its mission, HDR UK generates a diverse range of research outputs including but not limited to software, digital tools, changes to clinical guidelines, changes to public health policy, intellectual property, datasets, and more in addition to publications. All contributions to these outputs should be recognised, including those of patients, data generators, researchers, HDR UK and its funders. We particularly emphasise the importance of giving credit to those who collected the data and are making it available for reuse.

This policy further reflects our commitment to the FAIR data principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability).

Annex 2 details which and how outputs should be attributed.

Recognising and Rewarding the HDR UK Community

Ways in which the HDR UK community are recognised and rewarded, based on the outputs to which they contribute, include but are not limited to:

- **[HDR UK's Annual Awards](#)** which recognise good practises and celebrate the teams behind them. This includes awards for: impact, team science, public and patient involvement and engagement, reproducibility, and hidden roles.
- **[HDR UK's Impact Selections](#)** which reward outputs demonstrating research excellence Impact (e.g., on public health or healthcare), scale, team science, open science, public/patient impact and involvement, and equality, diversity and inclusion. Impact Selections are leveraged and made visible through HDR UK's wider communications channels.

Further Information or Clarity

HDR UK is keen to support attribution and communication around outputs. Please contact us at enquiries@hdruk.ac.uk if you need any support or clarification in this regard.

³ Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID): unique identifiers well-used in academia that will be helpful in tracking individuals in various systems.

Annex 1: How the HDR UK community is defined and policy adherence expectations for each group.

Group	Definition	Groups included	Policy adherence
Institute Members	Those directly supported by HDR UK funds, either with salary or research costs or 'in-kind' provision of time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Directors • Associate Directors • Scientists, technologists, fellows, researchers, analysts, trialists etc working on activities such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ HDR UK Infrastructure and Services ○ HDR UK Research Driver Projects ○ HDR UK Regional Networks ○ Programmes delivered in partnership with HDR UK or coordinated through HDR UK acting as host or secretariat (e.g. DARE UK, PEDRI, BHF Data Science Centre, Brain Health).⁴ • HDR UK MSc and PhD students 	Required to adhere to this policy , for outputs that have resulted from projects funded by HDR UK and/or for projects where at least part of their time has been directly funded by HDR UK
	Those directly supported by HDR UK funds, either with salary or 'in-kind' provision of time, who provide professional delivery roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional Leaders Group • PAs/EAs to Research Directors 	
	Those employed by HDR UK or seconded to HDR UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff, and Secondees 	
Affiliate Members	Collaborate or partner on HDR UK supported projects or activities, but not directly supported by HDR UK funds	Institutional Affiliate Members: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UK Health Data Research Alliance members • Academic collaborators (e.g. Alan Turing Institute) • Data & Infrastructure Partners (e.g. NHS England) Individual Affiliate Members:	Required to adhere to this policy in some cases , i.e. only for outputs that have resulted from being part of a team that includes HDR UK Institute Members

⁴ Outputs from these programmes may have specific attribution and publication requirements in addition to HDR UK's general guidance; please consult your collaboration agreement or programme manager for specific attribution requirements. See the [BHF Data Science Centre Publication Policy](#) as an example.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members of HDR UK Regional Networks and participants of the Black Internship Programme, not directly funded by HDR UK, but who directly engage with and contribute to HDR UK research teams or projects. 	
Users & Beneficiaries	Use and benefit from HDR UK research outputs, but not funded by HDR UK and not involved in developing HDR UK’s outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Users of algorithms, code, software and methodologies etc generated by Institute Members Users of HDR UK Infrastructure and Services 	Not required to adhere to this policy (unless they have been involved in a project that has been partially funded by HDR UK)

Annex 2. How to acknowledge HDR UK in research outputs.

Output	HDR UK affiliation	HDR UK attribution	Team science attribution	Patient & public data attribution
Code and related digital artefacts	<p>Make code (e.g. algorithms, analytical script, source code) and related digital artefacts (e.g. documents) available within the HDR UK GitHub repositories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to the open source software project by completing the ‘Submit OSS’ Issue Form. The default license for code in the HDR UK GitHub repositories is the MIT license, including forked and mirrored repositories. Otherwise, similarly liberal and open source licenses (such as Apache 2.0, BSD, Eclipse Public License) should be used, permitting anyone to benefit from, improve upon and redistribute the code. Any comments on code should always be polite and constructive, with collaboration and improvement as the intended outcome. We encourage the community to help in monitoring this culture. <p>Published results should include reference to the source code (as above) alongside a permanent, archived version of the source code at the time of publication (i.e. a ‘Software Availability’ statement).⁵</p>			n/a

⁵ Members are welcome to archive outputs, including [source code](#), in [HDR UK’s Zenodo Community Space](#) where it is safe, legal, and ethical to do so.

Output	HDR UK affiliation	HDR UK attribution	Team science attribution	Patient & public data attribution
Publications ^{3,6}	List HDR UK as one of the institutions to which you are affiliated	<p>Include in acknowledgements or funding section:</p> <p><i>'This work was supported by Health Data Research UK (insert award reference number where relevant), which is funded by the Medical Research Council (UKRI), the National Institute for Health Research, the British Heart Foundation, Cancer Research UK, the Economic and Social Research Council (UKRI), the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (UKRI), Health and Care Research Wales, Chief Scientist Office of the Scottish Government Health and Social Care Directorates, and Health and Social Care Research and Development Division (Public Health Agency, Northern Ireland).'</i></p> <p>A shortened version may be used if necessary:</p> <p><i>'This work was supported by Health Data Research UK (insert award reference number), an initiative funded by UK Research and Innovation, Department of Health and Social Care (England) and the devolved administrations, and leading medical research charities.'</i></p>	<p>List as authors each contributor to the work and acknowledge the contribution of each person using CASRAI's⁷ Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) system.</p> <p>Special care should be taken where applicable to include investigators located at institutions in Low and Middle Income Countries (LMICs) that led original study implementation.</p>	<p>Include in acknowledgements or funding section use MY data's data citation:</p> <p><i>'This work uses data provided by patients and collected by the NHS as part of their care and support'</i></p> <p>Or</p> <p><i>'This work uses data provided by patients and collected through clinical trials or as part of their care and support.'</i></p>
Datasets made available	n/a	A unique, persistent DOI should be generated and assigned to datasets and/or dataset metadata, listing HDR UK as a supporter, e.g. using a system such as DataCite . ³	List as author each contributor to the work.	n/a

⁶ Publications include journal articles/reviews, technical reports, technical standards, books, book chapters, conference proceedings/papers etc.

⁷ Consortia Advancing Standards in Research Administration Information (CASRAI).

Output	HDR UK affiliation	HDR UK attribution	Team science attribution	Patient & public data attribution
		<p>Published results should always include information about how to access the supporting data (i.e. a Data Availability statement). For data access facilitated via the Gateway, include the following:</p> <p><i>'Data discovery and access was facilitated by the Health Data Research Gateway' [insert year]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI: https://doi.org/10.57774/jriz-mn46 • Website: https://www.healthdatagateway.org/ 	Special care should be taken where applicable to include investigators located at institutions in Low and Middle Income Countries (LMICs) that led original study implementation.	
Tweets announcing HDR UK outputs ⁸	n/a	Tag @HDR_UK into the tweet	Consider including an appropriate hashtag to acknowledge teamwork in health data research, e.g. #teamscience or #oneinstitute	Consider including an appropriate hashtag to acknowledge use of patient/public data where appropriate, e.g. #datasaveslives
LinkedIn announcements ⁹ of outputs	n/a	Tag @Health Data Research UK into the post		
Summaries of outputs as presentations, media activity, press releases, events etc	Please see the 'HDR UK Brand and Style Guide' on the HDR UK website.			

⁸ HDR UK does not require publications to be announced on Twitter, but if they are this policy should be adhered to.

⁹ HDR UK does not require publications to be announced on LinkedIn, but if they are this policy should be adhered to.